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Citizens' Trust, E-Government, and Government Performance

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Abstract

E-government has become a central instrument for transforming public governance. Despite its growing importance, limited research has examined how e-government website quality shapes the relationship between citizens' trust in government and perceptions of government performance. This study investigates the mediating role of e-government website quality—operationalized through information quality, service quality, and system quality—within the extended DeLone and McLean IS success model (2003, 2004), drawing on Teo et al.'s (2008) framework. Analyzing survey data from Korean citizens ($n = 1,015$), we find that citizens' trust is positively associated with all three quality dimensions, but only information quality significantly mediates the trust–performance relationship. This mediation is stronger among e-government users and absent among non-users, underscoring the pivotal role of informational clarity and accuracy in translating trust into enhanced perceptions of government performance.

Keywords: e-Government; government trust; government performance; information quality; system quality; service quality

Introduction

The relationship between citizens' trust in government and government performance is complex and bidirectional (Van de Walle & Bouckaert, 2003). Trust legitimizes government, enabling more effective policy implementation; conversely, low trust erodes confidence and reduces compliance. The COVID-19 period starkly illustrated this dynamic, with protests over vaccine mandates and mask policies revealing how distrust undermines governance effectiveness (Hrbková & Kudrnáč, 2024). Perceptions of performance may also diverge from reality due to misinformation, political polarization, or entrenched negative attitudes.

E-government is increasingly recognized as a factor shaping this trust–performance relationship. The OECD (2003) defines e-government as 'the use of information and communication technologies, and particularly the Internet, as a tool to achieve better government.' High-quality e-government websites—for tax returns, passports, online voting, or public consultation—can enhance trust and performance perceptions by improving transparency, efficiency, and user engagement. Poorly designed platforms, conversely, signal governmental incompetence.

This study addresses three research questions: (1) Does citizens' trust in government increase their perceived evaluation of government performance? (2) Does e-government website quality mediate the relationship between trust and performance perceptions? (3) Does this effect differ by e-government usage? We test these questions using PLS-SEM on Korean survey data, employing the DeLone and McLean IS success model extended with trust as an antecedent.

Literature Review: Role of E-Government

E-government can bridge the gap between citizens' perceptions and actual government performance by providing real-time data and performance reports. Digitizing public services reduces bureaucracy, minimizes human error, and accelerates service delivery, increasing satisfaction and performance perceptions (Twizeyimana & Andersson, 2019; Alsarraf et al., 2022). This has been described as 'process-based trust': citizens who use government websites exhibit higher trust through enhanced interactions and perceptions of responsiveness (Tolbert & Mossberger, 2006). Cross-national research across 99 countries confirmed a significant association between e-government development, resource spending efficiency, and administrative process efficiency (Srivastava & Teo, 2007). E-government also limits face-to-face interactions, reducing opportunities for bribery and corruption, which enhances transparency and institutional confidence (Castro & Lopes, 2023).

Information quality is central to this process. Lee and Levy (2014: 89) identify key factors: 'information that is robust, accessible, relevant, comprehensive, current and has perceived value; and an information system which is efficient, flexible and has added-value.' Country studies reinforce this: in China, political trust predicted e-government adoption intentions (Mensah, 2020); in Jordan, trust in government and information quality drove e-service adoption (Abu-Shanab, 2014); and in Greece, trust in e-government and perceived usefulness were among the most significant adoption factors (Chatzoglou et al., 2015).

Theoretical Model and Hypotheses

We adopt Teo et al.'s (2008) framework, which integrates the DeLone and McLean IS success model (2003, 2004) with trust in e-government. Three quality dimensions are used: information quality ('citizens' assessment of whether website information is accurate, valid and timely'); system quality ('citizens' perception of the technical performance of the website'); and service quality ('citizens' perceptions of the overall service delivered by a government agency'). Teo et al. found trust in government to be an important antecedent to trust in e-government, which positively affects all three quality dimensions. We extend this model to examine how quality dimensions in turn shape government performance perceptions.

Trust and Website Quality Dimensions

Attribution theory (Kelley, 1973) provides grounding for the trust–information quality link: users who experience reliable government information attribute it to internal stable qualities (consistency), social validation (consensus), and uniqueness of government sources (distinctiveness). Trust in the benevolence,

integrity, and ability of government (Salo et al., 2007) makes citizens more likely to perceive information as accurate, valid, and timely. For system quality, trust reduces cognitive barriers to engaging with technical systems and increases favorable perceptions of functionality, navigation, and accessibility (Gefen et al., 2008; Saha et al., 2012). For service quality, trust enhances satisfaction with government services and willingness to engage with agencies, reinforcing perceptions of responsiveness and empathy (Papadomichelaki & Mentzas, 2012). Based on this literature:

H1: Citizens' trust in government will be positively related with perceived information quality of e-government websites.

H2: Citizens' trust in government will be positively related with perceived system quality of e-government websites.

H3: Citizens' trust in government will be positively related with perceived service quality of e-government websites.

Website Quality and Government Performance Perceptions

When government websites provide reliable, clear, and useful information, citizens perceive government as transparent, competent, and responsive (McKinney et al., 2002; Zheng et al., 2009). System quality—ease of navigation, accessibility, and functionality—signals efficiency and responsiveness, shaping performance evaluations (Saha et al., 2012; Hariguna et al., 2017). Good service quality demonstrates government commitment to the public (Zhang & Prybutok, 2005; Scott et al., 2011). We therefore hypothesize:

H4: E-government information quality will be positively related with perceptions of government performance.

H5: E-government system quality will be positively related with perceptions of government performance.

H6: E-government service quality will be positively related with perceptions of government performance.

Citizens' Trust and Government Performance

Meta-analysis of 72 empirical studies across 100 countries shows the performance–trust link is stronger in low power–distance societies and robust across objective and subjective performance measures (Zhang et al., 2022). Recent evidence from Hong Kong found that trust in an institution contributes more strongly to perceived effectiveness than the reverse (Xiao et al., 2024). Analysis of Integrated Values Survey data across 100+ countries found trust in government positively correlated with voluntary policy compliance, enabling state effectiveness with lower enforcement costs—conceptualized as a 'reputational asset' (Besley & Dray, 2024: 2228). We therefore hypothesize:

H7: Citizens' trust in government will be positively related with their perceptions of government performance.

<<Figure 1: Path Diagram – insert here>>

Research Methodology

Data

We draw on the Center for Future Government survey, South Korea (CFG, 2018), collected from October 19 to November 2, 2018 by Korean Research using stratified random sampling based on gender, age, education, and residence from a panel of approximately 400,000. The Computer-Assisted Web Interview (CAWI) sample comprises 1,015 adults aged 20+ across 17 provinces and cities: 49.2% male, 50.8% female; age balanced across 20s–60s; 56% with a four-year college degree or higher. Respondent demographics are reported in Table A1.

Variables and Measurement

All attitudinal variables were assessed using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Government performance perception (DV) is measured with three items (e.g., 'Government achieves policy goals effectively'; $\alpha = 0.88$). Government trust (IV) is measured with three items capturing acceptance of government decisions and willingness to endure policy-induced disadvantages ($\alpha = 0.77$), consistent with the Trust in Government Measure (Burns et al., 2023). The three website quality mediators follow Teo et al. (2008): information quality (six items: clarity, accuracy, usefulness, timeliness, reliability, sufficiency; $\alpha = 0.90$); system quality (three items: usability, navigation, accessibility; $\alpha = 0.83$); service quality (two items: dependability, assurance; $\alpha = 0.72$). Survey items are displayed in Table 1.

<<Table 1: Items & Variables – insert here>>

Measurement Validation

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with varimax rotation yielded a five-factor solution. Government performance items loaded on Factor 2 (0.75–0.81), information quality on Factor 1 (0.69–0.79), system quality on Factor 3 (0.53–0.72), and government trust on Factor 4 (0.59–0.70). However, service quality items exhibited cross-loadings on Factor 1 (0.60–0.62), indicating insufficient discriminant validity. Following Hair et al. (2012), service quality items were removed and the EFA rerun (Panel B), confirming convergent and discriminant validity for the remaining four factors.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) showed all items loading significantly on their constructs (standardized loadings: 0.597–0.871). Panel B fit statistics: CFI = 0.96, TLI = 0.95, RMSEA = 0.063, SRMR = 0.033, CD = 0.999—all meeting accepted thresholds. Average Variance Extracted (AVE: 0.53–0.70) exceeded the 0.50 threshold and Composite Reliability (CR: 0.69–0.85) approached or exceeded 0.70 for all constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity was confirmed as square-root AVE exceeded inter-construct correlations in Panel B. Service quality failed these criteria in Panel A, confirming its exclusion. Results are summarized in Tables 2–5.

<<Tables 2–5: EFA, CFA, Descriptive Statistics, Correlations – insert here>>

Statistical Method

Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed, using Stata 16. PLS-SEM is appropriate for complex, prediction-oriented models and is robust with non-normal data (Chin, 1998; Hair et al., 2021). Results are reported for the full sample and for subgroups of e-government users ($n = 743$) and non-users ($n = 272$).

Results

Table 6 presents standardized path coefficients from two model specifications: Panel A includes all variables; Panel B excludes service quality. Indirect effects from bootstrapping (1,000 repetitions) are reported in Table 7.

Trust and website quality: Citizens' trust significantly and positively predicts all three quality dimensions (Panel A). Trust → information quality ($\beta = 0.344, p < 0.001$); trust → system quality ($\beta = 0.299, p < 0.001$); trust → service quality ($\beta = 0.297, p < 0.001$). Effects are consistent across users and non-users, with slightly stronger coefficients among non-users, suggesting that trust plays a more pronounced role when direct service experience is absent.

Mediating role of website quality: Information quality significantly mediates the trust–performance relationship in the overall sample ($\beta = 0.111, p < 0.01$) and among users ($\beta = 0.130, p = 0.006$), but not among non-users ($\beta = 0.086, p = 0.272$). System quality shows a weak but significant overall effect ($\beta = 0.076, p < 0.05$), though group-specific effects are non-significant. Service quality does not significantly predict performance in any group. Panel B results confirm robustness: information quality mediates the trust–performance link among users ($\beta = 0.128, p < 0.01$); system quality retains a modest overall effect ($\beta = 0.074, p = 0.031$).

Bootstrapping confirms that information quality significantly mediates the trust–performance relationship (indirect effect = 0.040, $p = 0.006$ in Panel B), and system quality shows a small but significant indirect effect (0.024, $p = 0.048$). Service quality shows no significant indirect effect.

Direct trust effect: Government trust is the strongest direct predictor of performance perceptions across all models ($\beta = 0.521, p < 0.001$ overall; $\beta = 0.517$ for users; $\beta = 0.532$ for non-users). As shown in Table A2, approximately 89.8% of trust's total effect operates directly, with only 10.2% mediated through website quality dimensions.

<<Tables 6–8 and Figure 2: SEM Results – insert here>>

Table 8. Summary of Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Finding	Implication
H1: Trust → Information Quality	Supported ($\beta = 0.344, p < .001$)	Trust drives perceived information quality
H2: Trust → System Quality	Supported ($\beta = 0.299, p < .001$)	Trust improves evaluation of technical reliability
H3: Trust → Service Quality	Construct removed	Insufficient discriminant validity
H4: Info. Quality → Performance	Supported ($\beta = 0.108, p < .01$; users: $\beta = 0.128$)	Better information quality improves performance perceptions
H5: System Quality → Performance	Partially supported ($\beta = 0.074, p < .05$)	Small but positive effect; weaker than information quality
H6: Service Quality → Performance	Construct removed	Future research needed
H7: Trust → Performance	Strongly supported ($\beta = 0.521, p < .001$)	Trust is the dominant driver (~90% direct effect)

Discussion

This study examined how citizens' trust influences e-government website quality perceptions and, in turn, government performance evaluations. The findings confirm information quality as the pivotal mediator: its effect on the trust–performance relationship is significant among e-government users but absent among non-users, indicating that actual platform engagement is necessary for informational dimensions to shape performance perceptions. This aligns with research emphasizing information transparency and accessibility in digital governance (Bannister & Connolly, 2014).

System quality exhibited a modest but significant indirect effect, consistent with prior IS success model research (Petter et al., 2008; Wang & Liao, 2008). Service quality showed no significant effects, and its exclusion in Panel B improved model robustness—suggesting that citizens prioritize informational and technical dimensions over transactional service aspects when evaluating government performance (Grimmelikhuijsen & Meijer, 2014). Critically, government trust remained the strongest direct predictor of performance perceptions, reinforcing that e-government platforms enhance but do not replace the foundational role of trust (Bouckaert & Van de Walle, 2003).

The study makes three contributions. First, it extends the DeLone and McLean IS success model by integrating trust as an antecedent and demonstrating differentiated mediating roles of quality dimensions. Second, using Korean survey data, it provides evidence that information quality is the pivotal mediator contingent on actual e-government use. Third, the subgroup analysis advances process-based trust theory (Tolbert & Mossberger, 2006; Porumbescu, 2016a, 2016b) by showing e-government quality effects materialize only for active users—demonstrating the conditional nature of digital governance effects.

Limitations include: cross-sectional design limiting causal inference; reliance on self-reported measures; and focus on Korea, limiting generalizability. Future research should employ longitudinal designs, incorporate behavioral usage data, conduct comparative cross-national studies, and explore whether service quality becomes more salient in contexts with richer transactional e-government services.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study demonstrates that information quality is the key mechanism through which citizens' trust is translated into performance perceptions, particularly among e-government users. Since direct trust effects (~89.8%) substantially outweigh e-government mediation (~10.2%), governments should prioritize trust-building alongside website improvements.

Key policy implications are as follows. First, invest in trust-building: transparency initiatives (publishing spending, performance metrics), robust oversight mechanisms, and honest communication strategies are more impactful than website redesigns. Second, prioritize content over features: information quality is the only website dimension significantly affecting performance perceptions—governments should invest in content specialists, fact-checkers, and plain-language editors rather than sophisticated interactive features. Third, address the digital divide: non-users rely entirely on direct trust relationships, so traditional service channels must be maintained alongside digital ones, and digital literacy programmes targeted at older adults, rural communities, and low-income groups are essential. Fourth, maintain basic functionality: the weak system quality–performance link suggests technical upgrades yield limited returns; reliable basic functionality matters more than advanced features. Finally, recognize that digital transformation alone cannot resolve the trust deficit—it must be combined with broader governance reform, accountability measures, and improved service delivery.

Theoretically, the study confirms trust as a foundational input to performance perceptions rather than an outcome of good governance (Van de Walle & Bouckaert, 2003; Zhang et al., 2022), consistent with the

'reputational asset' framework (Besley & Dray, 2024) and evidence from Hong Kong (Xiao et al., 2024). The extension of the DeLone and McLean IS success model into public governance underscores the primacy of information quality over system and service quality (Lee & Levy, 2014; Tolbert & Mossberger, 2006). The absence of service quality as a valid construct further suggests that e-government in many contexts remains primarily an informational infrastructure—theories of digital governance should distinguish between information-based and interaction-based trust-building mechanisms (Twizeyimana & Andersson, 2019).